

RESEARCH DIGEST

Uncertainty-Aware Grid Planning in the Real World: A Method Enabling Large-Scale, Two-Stage Adaptive Robust Optimization for Capacity Expansion Planning

Gabriel Mantegna, Emil Dimanchev, Filippo Pecci, Neha Patankar, Jesse Jenkins
Princeton University | March 2026

Read the full paper at: <http://arxiv.org/abs/2603.00394>

Motivation

Today's grid planners are challenged with making multi-billion-dollar grid infrastructure decisions amidst **significant uncertainty**. Key drivers of uncertainty include **demand growth** due to data centers and electrification, and **rapidly changing resource availabilities and costs** due to siting constraints, policy uncertainty, and technological developments.

Despite this environment of significant uncertainty, current grid planning processes use **deterministic modeling**, which was primarily designed for a previous era of predictable load growth and minimal resource additions. These models rely on studying specific scenarios assuming perfect foresight of future conditions, which makes them **incapable of supporting the development of robust, flexible, and adaptable decisions** in response to future uncertainty.

Deterministic modeling processes end up with infrastructure decisions that are **over-optimized for one specific future**, with **limited adaptability** if the future turns out different from how we expect. The consequences of this for ratepayers can be significant: over-optimized decisions could lead to **stranded assets, outages, and higher power prices**. Jurisdictions such as California are already seeing the consequences of insufficient proactive planning today in the acute scarcity of interconnection capacity for new power generation and storage projects seeking to connect to the grid and the high rate of project cancellations after facing larger than expected interconnection upgrade costs.¹

Modeling frameworks that directly incorporate uncertainty, broadly known as **decision-making under uncertainty** or **uncertainty-aware** methods, are available as a modern alternative to deterministic planning. These methods are widely used in other fields, such as finance. These frameworks **incorporate future uncertainties into the models themselves**, helping to identify flexible and adaptable decisions.

However, electricity system **capacity expansion models that directly incorporate uncertainty are rarely used in practice**. This is due to a technology transfer gap and a lack of methods that work at large

¹ For more details, see a recent Berkeley Lab study on the subject: <https://emp.lbl.gov/queues>

scale. In this paper we **demonstrate the impact of incorporating uncertainty-aware methods into capacity expansion models**, and introduce a technique for improving the methods’ scalability.

Methods

In this study, we demonstrate the feasibility of applying decision-making-under-uncertainty techniques to a **real-world, large-scale capacity expansion problem for the state of California**. We use the open-source GenX model that is benchmarked to replicate the RESOLVE model used by the California Public Utilities Commission to inform generation and transmission planning for the State. By demonstrating our methods with a real-world example, we show that these methods **can be implemented into real-world planning processes without modification**. We also introduce a novel method for improving the scalability and applicability of existing techniques.

Findings

We find that modeling that directly incorporates uncertainty into California’s grid planning identifies **increased transmission investment as a key lever to improve robustness and adaptability**, while helping to **avoid potential affordability and outage risks** that current deterministic planning processes may be exposing ratepayers to. We also find that our method for improving scalability provides a pathway to incorporating uncertainty-aware modeling into even more granular and detailed models than those used in current California integrated resource planning.

Figure 1 shows that our robust optimization-based model identifies additional transmission investment as a key lever to increase robustness to key uncertainties.² Meanwhile, Figure 2 shows how these more robust portfolios require **a relatively small (<\$1B annually or <0.4 ¢/kWh) increased investment in transmission expansion in California but may result in over \$20B (8 ¢/kWh) in annual savings³** if key uncertainties turn out worse than foreseen by California’s existing deterministic modeling framework.

Figure 1: First-stage resource builds in deterministic vs robust models, with varying levels of robustness. Γ , or “Gamma”, is a parameter that controls the robustness of the model. Higher Γ means that resulting portfolios are more prepared for multiple uncertainties to simultaneously be different from what we expect in a deterministic case.²

² In Fig. 1, the rightmost bar identifies a lower MW amount of transmission, while shifting investment to more costly transmission assets, as shown in Fig. 2.

³ This figure includes non-served-energy costs; the figure changes to \$5B (2 ¢/kWh) when non-served-energy costs are excluded.

Figure 2: First stage cost increase by scenario (left), and second stage performance from stress-testing (right). In the right plot, the “With NSE” bars show second-stage costs with non-served-energy (NSE) costs included, while the “Without NSE” bars show second-stage costs without non-served-energy costs included.

Policy recommendations

- Grid infrastructure planners should adopt **decision-making-under-uncertainty methods, such as the robust optimization methods used in this study**, in capacity expansion planning models. These models help identify robust, flexible, and adaptable infrastructure decisions and enable **conversations amongst decision-makers about trade-offs between near-term costs and long-term risks**.
- A regulatory framework that **emphasizes balancing costs with risks can help to preserve affordability across a range of future scenarios**. The current grid planning framework in California does not employ the robust planning amidst uncertainty strategies demonstrated in this study, which may expose ratepayers to significant cost and reliability risks.
- As part of a robust planning framework, grid planners should be **encouraged to stress-test candidate near-term decisions over a range of possible futures**, particularly in the context of long-lead-time decisions such as transmission expansion. This framing also aligns well with the requirements of FERC Order 1920-A, although it is crucial that planners use scenarios for stress-testing of near-term decisions, rather than simply developing different deterministic portfolios for each future scenario.

About the authors

Gabriel Mantegna is a Maeder Graduate Fellow in Energy and the Environment at the Andlinger Center for Energy and the Environment, as well as a PhD candidate in Mechanical and Aerospace Engineering, at Princeton University.

Emil Dimanchev is a postdoctoral research associate in the Andlinger Center for Energy and the Environment at Princeton University.

Filippo Pecci is a scientist at the RFF-CMCC European Institute on Economics and the Environment in Milan, Italy.

Neha Patankar is an assistant professor in the School of Systems Science and Industrial Engineering at Binghamton University.

Jesse D. Jenkins is an associate professor at Princeton University with joint appointments in the Department of Mechanical and Aerospace Engineering and Andlinger Center for Energy and the Environment.

Funding for this manuscript was provided by the Paul A. Maeder 75 Fund for Innovation in Energy and the Environment, the Andlinger Center for Energy and the Environment, Sonoma Clean Power, and Peninsula Clean Energy.